

Original Research

Angioplasty of Saphenous Vein Grafts After Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery: A Single-Center Retrospective Study with Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

In many patients undergoing coronary artery bypass graft surgery (CABG), venous saphenous grafts (SVG) are used in addition to arterial grafts. Treatment of degenerated and occluded venous grafts is complex and challenging. Angioplasty on occluded venous bypass grafts involves a high rate of complications (such as massive distal embolization).

Objectives:

To review the demographic data, risk factors, outcomes, and complications of SVG use in CABG surgery, and on this basis to build an algorithm for optimal treatment.

Methods:

A retrospective study of patients who underwent angioplasty of saphenous vein grafts (SVGs) between 2005 and 2015 in a tertiary care hospital. Patients were divided into two groups: 2005–2009 (group A) and 2010–2015 (group B), and the comparison was performed according to demographic data, risk factors, time from CABG, as well as angiographic features.

Results:

Among the 238 patients, 226 (95%) were male, with a mean age of 68±22 years. 74.4% suffered from hypertension, 56.3% from diabetes mellitus, 17.2% from chronic kidney disease, and 99% had a history of previous myocardial infarction. 62% of patients were admitted due to ACS.

Distal protection devices were used in only 31 (22%) patients. Intervention was performed mainly on the right and circumflex coronary arteries.

A lower amount of contrast was used in group B (186 vs 137 mL, p=0.0018). There was more frequent use of covered stents in group B (18.8% vs 2.1%, p=0.003), as well as increased use of protection devices (36.4% vs 9.5%, p=0.0002).

Conclusions:

The progression of technologies, mainly the use of protection devices, lowered the rate of complications during intervention on SVGs. This was also reflected in the reduced amount of contrast material used and lower incidence of kidney injury. Over the years, there has been a tendency to treat more severely ill patients with longer time since surgery (“older” grafts).

Keywords: coronary artery bypass grafting; saphenous vein graft; angioplasty; complications; distal embolization; protection devices; stents; acute coronary syndrome

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery bypass graft surgery (CABG) has been performed for over four decades in millions of patients worldwide and is well established today. Despite increased experience and the growing use of arterial grafts in recent years, venous grafts are still widely used. As a result, disease of the venous graft (saphenous vein graft disease – SVGD) continues to be a leading cause of symptomatic coronary artery disease after this surgery and usually occurs approximately 5–10 years after surgery (1).

In the first year after surgery, venous grafts remain patent in about 80–85% of cases, with an average patency duration of 8–9 years (2,3), followed by a 50% reduction in long-term patency thereafter. Repeat surgery is not justified in most cases; therefore, catheter-based intervention is, in most cases, the preferred strategy for revascularization.

Numerous studies and meta-analyses have demonstrated pathophysiological and clinical differences between diseases of venous grafts and native coronary arteries. The correct selection of patients, initial treatment strategy, stent type, and the use of adjunctive devices for revascularization, such as protection devices, play an important role in achieving optimal results both in the short and long term. However, even with these treatments, SVGD remains a significant clinical problem, with graft occlusion rates reported as high as 89% in the first year after surgery and up to 61% at approximately 10 years (18).

METHODS

In the Database Unit of Hadassah Hospital, 238 patients who had undergone intervention on venous grafts during the last decade were identified. Patients were divided into two groups: 2005 to 2009 (Group A) and 2010 to 2015 (Group B).

The comparison was performed according to demographic data (age, sex), risk factors (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, kidney failure), time from CABG, as well as angiographic features, severity of coronary disease, amount of contrast material used, and final result (according to restoration of flow) (Table 1).

Table 1. Patient Demographic, Clinical, and Angiographic Characteristics

	All (n=238)	Group A (n=149)	Group B (n=89)	p-value
Demographics	68 ± 22	67 ± 21	68 ± 21	NS
Age (years, mean ± SD)	68 ± 22	67 ± 21	68 ± 21	NS
Female gender (%)	5.0	4.7	5.6	NS
Hypertension (%)	74.4	77.9	68.5	NS
Diabetes mellitus (%)	56.3	53.7	60.7	NS
Prior myocardial infarction (%)	99.2	98.6	98.9	NS
Congestive Heart Failure(data in 65%)	91.5	83.1	98.8	NS
Renal failure (%)	17.2	19.5	13.5	NS
Clinical presentation	Clinical presentation			
Stable angina (%)	38.0	40.4	33.8	NS
ACS (%)	62.0	59.6	66.2	NS
Catheterization features	Catheterization features			
Percentage of all angioplasties (%)	–	–	4.3	–
Severity of coronary disease (%)	92.6	83.1	98.8	NS
TIMI flow 2/3 (%)	75.0	81.2	67.8	NS
Balloon dilatation (%)	59.5	57.2	63.1	NS
Integriilin use (%)	6.3	8.0	7.0	NS
Nitroglycerin use (%)	9.2	13.0	9.0	NS
Covered stents (%)	4.3	2.1	18.8	0.003
Protection device (%)	22.1	9.5	36.4	0.0002
Good angiographic result (%)	93.7	95.9	91.0	NS
Contrast amount (mean, ml)	174.8	187.6	196.7	NS
Culprit lesion	21.0	21.9	19.3	NS
LAD (%)	37.1	32.9	44.6	NS
CX (%)	41.9	45.2	36.1	NS

*Data available in 65% of patients. NS = not statistically significant, ACS= acute coronary syndrome, BMS= bare-metal stent, TIMI= Thrombolysis in Myocardial infarction, LAD= left anterior descending artery, RCA= right coronary artery, CX= circumflex artery

RESULTS

In the Database Unit of Hadassah Hospital, there were 238 patients who had undergone intervention on venous grafts during the last decade. They were divided into two groups: 2005 to 2009 (Group A) and 2010 to 2015 (Group B), and the comparison was performed according to demographic data (age, sex), risk factors (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, kidney failure), time from CABG, as well as angiographic features, severity of coronary disease, amount of contrast material used, and final result (according to restoration of flow) (Table 1).

It was found that most of the population were men (95%) and had a previous MI. A higher proportion of diabetic patients was observed in the later years, but without statistical significance. There was a low rate of chronic kidney disease (17%) in both groups. There was a slightly longer period after CABG before intervention (10 vs 14 years).

Sixty-two percent of the patients were admitted with ACS. The severity of the disease (assessed by lesion length and distal flow) was at least moderate in 83% of the population, with no difference between the groups.

The use of protection devices was low in the overall population (13%), with 9.5% in the early group and 36.4% in the later group ($p=0.0002$). There was no difference in the rate of post-dilatation or use of vasodilators.

Intervention was performed on similar coronary arteries, and less frequently on LAD lesions, likely due to the presence of LIMA grafts. There was more frequent use of covered stents in the later group (2.1% vs 18.8%).

Good flow was achieved in both groups (95%). A larger amount of contrast material was used in the earlier group (186 vs 137 mL).

There was a low rate of complications and death during one-year follow-up, likely influenced by the retrospective nature of the analysis.

Figure 1. Temporal Trends in Time from CABG to SVG Intervention (2005–2015)

Mean interval (years) between coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) and percutaneous intervention on saphenous vein grafts (SVG) during the study period.

Antiplatelet therapy at discharge was most commonly a combination of aspirin and Plavix (80% vs 73% in early and later groups, respectively). The lower use of this combination in later years was mainly explained by the introduction of newer antiplatelet agents (ticagrelor and prasugrel).

DISCUSSION

Over the years, the development of technology and accumulated experience in invasive treatment approaches have increased the success rate to more than 90%. Catheterization and intervention on venous grafts currently account for approximately 5.7% of all therapeutic catheterizations (4).

Venous graft failure (VGF) has multiple contributing factors, both clinical and surgical (5–9). A study examining factors associated with increased incidence of VGF found that prolonged surgery duration and poor quality of the target artery were significant predictors of venous graft failure (3,4).

Additional studies have identified patient-related characteristics such as advanced age, female gender, heart failure, and hypercholesterolemia as predictors of venous graft failure (10–12). Surgical variables, including preservation temperature of the graft, multiple anastomoses, damage to the distal vessel, and narrowing of the target artery, have also been implicated. It should be noted that many of these analyses were performed at a time when antiplatelet therapy was less commonly used (13–15).

In terms of long-term venous thrombosis, accelerated fibrosis and advanced atherosclerosis are major contributors to acute thrombosis (46,19). Compared with angioplasty of native arteries, intervention on venous grafts is more complex and associated with a higher rate of periprocedural myocardial infarction due to atheromatous and thrombotic material within the graft (20).

The most common immediate complication of venous graft angioplasty is distal embolization, likely due to friable plaque mixed with thrombus. This may result in no-flow or slow-flow phenomena, which can cause acute and extensive ischemia with ST-segment changes, with an acute coronary syndrome rate of approximately 30% (21,22,23,36).

There is no clear correlation between graft size and distal embolization, likely due to the role of inflammatory mediators and left ventricular dysfunction (36,37).

Venous graft occlusion may present in various forms, including elevated cardiac enzymes, acute heart failure, arrhythmias, stable angina, acute coronary syndrome without ST elevation (NSTEMI), ST elevation (STEMI), and cardiac arrest (16,17,57,58).

Stress testing, with or without imaging, may suggest ischemia but cannot reliably distinguish between native artery and graft disease (60). Angiography remains the gold standard for diagnosis and determining the need for revascularization.

Venous graft disease is a leading cause of mortality after bypass surgery. Three main management approaches are recognized: conservative treatment, percutaneous intervention, and repeat CABG (46).

Anticoagulation strategies have evolved significantly since the 1990s. Previously, treatment included aspirin, dipyridamole, and warfarin, often combined with heparin in high-risk patients. Currently, management relies mainly on potent antiplatelet agents (64).

Routine use of glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitors has not shown benefit in reducing distal embolization and is associated with increased bleeding risk (65–67).

Two major issues remain debated in patients undergoing intervention after CABG (93). The first is the preferred target for intervention. Intervention on friable SVG lesions is associated with high rates of restenosis and target vessel failure (94–97). Some retrospective studies suggest that intervention on native arteries may be preferable in selected cases (98,99).

The second issue is the optimal stent type (47,93). Stenting is clearly superior to balloon angioplasty, which is associated with high restenosis rates (up to 70% at 6 months) (3).

The SAVED trial demonstrated improved outcomes with stenting compared to balloon angioplasty, including reduction in major adverse cardiac events (MACE) (47).

Drug-eluting stents (DES) have reduced the need for repeat interventions and MACE compared to bare-metal stents (BMS), although mortality differences remain unclear (48–50). Their use has increased significantly since 2009 (42,44,45,62).

Periprocedural complications were lower in the DES group (4.2% vs 5.9%, $p < 0.001$) (26,33,40,43).

Studies comparing standard stents with paclitaxel-coated stents did not show differences in mortality but demonstrated reduced repeat interventions and acute coronary events with DES over a follow-up of approximately 34 months (42).

PTFE-covered stents may help reduce distal embolization, although evidence remains limited (51–54). Other stent types, such as SESAME and MGuard, have not demonstrated consistent long-term benefits (55,56).

Another debated issue is whether to treat multiple lesions within a single graft or multiple grafts during the same procedure; current evidence suggests no significant difference (63).

Higher mortality observed in BMS groups may be related to shorter duration of antiplatelet therapy (DELAYED-RRISC trial) (43).

Potential mechanisms contributing to adverse outcomes with DES include unstable lesions, inflammatory responses, and late aneurysm formation (3,92,97).

In the absence of extensive collateral circulation, distal occlusion and thrombus formation remain common during SVG interventions (57). Therefore, careful consideration should be given to whether intervention on the graft or native artery is more appropriate.

In cases where intervention is not feasible, conservative management may be considered if symptoms are controlled and risk of myocardial infarction is low (57).

Given the lack of large randomized trials, optimal treatment strategies remain uncertain. However, reduction in MACE may be achieved through:

1. Careful selection of lesions

2. Use of embolic protection devices (EBD)
3. Use of smaller diameter stents
4. Pre-treatment with vasodilators (34,59)

Perforation during SVG intervention occurs in approximately 1% of cases and is more frequent in the presence of aneurysms (68–70).

The no-reflow phenomenon occurs in approximately 20% of cases and is associated with increased mortality, ventricular dysfunction, arrhythmias, and heart failure (71,79).

This phenomenon is classified into structural (microvascular damage) and functional (vasospasm and embolization) types (80,81,89).

The underlying mechanisms include endothelial injury, oxidative stress, and release of vasoactive substances (72,73).

Management includes hemodynamic support, oxygenation, and administration of vasodilators (83).

Pharmacologic responses vary, but venous graft lesions often respond better to agents such as adenosine and verapamil (78,79,85–87,90).

Nitric oxide donors, such as nitroprusside, have shown mixed results, with no significant improvement in flow but potential reduction in clinical events (82,91).

CONCLUSIONS

In many patients with ischemic heart disease requiring revascularization by coronary artery bypass graft surgery (CABG), saphenous vein grafts (SVG) are frequently used in addition to arterial grafts. Venous grafts tend to have higher rates of occlusion compared to arterial grafts, often requiring revascularization 5–10 years after surgery.

Venous graft stenosis may present in a wide range of clinical manifestations, including sudden onset heart failure, arrhythmia, stable angina, acute coronary syndrome without ST elevation, and cardiac arrest.

The treatment of degenerated venous grafts is complex and challenging. Only a minority of patients undergo repeat surgery, while a significant proportion are treated with catheter-based intervention. Angioplasty of venous grafts is associated with a high rate of complications (such as massive distal embolization), and therefore careful procedural planning is essential.

Previous studies have evaluated the use of bare-metal stents (BMS), drug-eluting stents (DES), and covered stents; however, the optimal strategy remains unresolved.

We retrospectively examined a cohort of patients undergoing angioplasty for venous grafts over the past decade (2005–2015) at Hadassah Medical Center, Jerusalem.

The results showed that most patients were male, with a high prevalence of diabetes and increasing comorbidity in recent years. Most patients also had hypertension and mild to moderate heart failure, and a history of ischemic heart disease prior to the index admission.

There has been an increase over time in the interval since bypass surgery, possibly reflecting greater use of arterial grafts and advances in surgical techniques.

Approximately 62% of patients were admitted with acute coronary syndrome, while the remainder underwent elective procedures based on stress testing or stable angina symptoms. This proportion remained stable over time.

More than 90% of grafts had at least moderate stenosis. The use of protection devices was relatively low overall (13%) but increased consistently over time. Balloon dilatation was performed in approximately 60% of procedures, with similar rates across both groups. The use of vasodilators remained relatively stable (15–18%).

Interventions were most commonly performed on LCX and RCA territories, with fewer procedures on LAD, likely due to LIMA grafting. The use of drug-coated stents increased significantly in recent years.

Successful restoration of flow was achieved in approximately 95% of procedures, with similar outcomes between groups.

A reduction in contrast volume over time suggests improved procedural efficiency and operator experience.

Procedural complications were low throughout the follow-up period. Most patients were discharged on dual antiplatelet therapy (aspirin and Plavix), although its use decreased over time with increasing adoption of newer antiplatelet agents such as prasugrel and ticagrelor.

The influence of stent type and protection device use suggests a shift toward treatment of more complex patients with older grafts, supported by increased use of advanced devices and techniques.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

A major limitation of this study is its retrospective, single-center design. In addition, data on the severity of heart failure and types of stents used in earlier years are incomplete.

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DECLARATIONS

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Due to the retrospective nature of the study and the use of anonymized data, formal ethical approval and informed consent were waived by the institutional review board.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests (Conflict of Interest)

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the conception and design of the study, data collection, analysis, and interpretation. All authors were involved in drafting the manuscript and critically revising

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